

Effects of simulated Secondary Organic Aerosol Water on PM₁ levels and composition over US

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Abstract. Water is a key component of atmospheric aerosol, affecting many aerosol processes including gas/particle partitioning of semi-volatile compounds. Water related to secondary organic aerosol (SOAW) is often neglected in atmospheric chemical transport models and is not considered in gas-to-particle partitioning calculations for inorganic species. We use a new inorganic aerosol thermodynamics model, ISORROPIA-lite, which considers the effects of SOAW, to perform chemical transport model simulations for a year over the continental United States to quantify its effects on aerosol mass concentration and composition. SOAW can increase average fine aerosol water levels up to a factor of two when secondary organic aerosol (SOA) is a major PM₁ component. This is often the case in the south-eastern U.S where SOA concentrations are higher. Although the annual average impact of this added water on total dry PM₁ concentrations due to increased partitioning of nitrate and ammonium is small (up to 0.1 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), total dry PM₁ increases of up to 2 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (with nitrate levels increases up to 200%) can occur when RH levels and PM₁ concentrations are high.

1. Introduction

Atmospheric particulate matter with aerodynamic diameter smaller than 1 μm (PM₁) has adverse effects on public health, climate and ecosystem productivity (Pye et al., 2020; Baker et al., 2021; Guo et al., 2021). PM₁ is composed of thousands of organic compounds, black carbon (BC), and inorganic components such as sulfate (SO₄²⁻),

36 nitrate (NO_3^-), ammonium (NH_4^+) and chloride (Cl^-) (Seinfeld and Pandis, 2006).
37 Ambient aerosol is mostly composed of water which is determined by the chemical
38 equilibrium of water vapor with the aerosol constituents (Liao and Seinfeld, 2005;
39 Carlton and Turpin, 2013; Bian et al., 2014; Guo et al., 2015; Bougiatioti et al., 2016;
40 Nguyen et al., 2016; Guo et al., 2017; Deetz et al., 2018; Kuang et al., 2018; Song et
41 al., 2018; Wu et al., 2018; Pye et al., 2020; Gopinath et al., 2022). Aerosol liquid
42 water directly affects the PM sensitivity and dry deposition rates, with direct
43 implications for emissions control policy (Nenes et al., 2020; Nenes et al., 2021; Sun
44 et al., 2021).

45 The hygroscopicity parameter (κ), which expresses the ability of a PM
46 component to absorb water, is an effective approach for the parameterization of the
47 water uptake of atmospheric PM that is a mixture of organic and inorganic species
48 (Petters and Kreidenweis, 2007). Although organic aerosol (OA) is less hygroscopic
49 than inorganic salts, it can still contribute significantly to the total aerosol water (Guo
50 et al., 2015; Bougiatioti et al., 2016; Jathar et al., 2016; Li et al., 2019) or can even
51 become the dominant contributor at lower ambient relative humidity (Jin et al., 2020).
52 Previous studies have demonstrated that secondary organic aerosol (SOA) is a lot
53 more hygroscopic ($0.1 \leq \kappa \leq 0.3$) than primary organic aerosol (POA) ($\kappa \leq 0.01$) and
54 is mainly responsible for the corresponding OA water (Petters et al., 2006; Koehler et
55 al., 2009; Chang et al., 2010; Jathar et al., 2016; Kuang et al., 2020; Li et al., 2020).

56 SOAW can enhance secondary inorganic aerosol concentrations assisting in
57 their partitioning in the particulate phase to satisfy equilibrium. However, such effects
58 are not considered in thermodynamic modules used for the simulation of gas-to-
59 particle partitioning of inorganic species in chemical transport models. Evidence
60 exists however that fine aerosol nitrate and ammonium concentrations can increase in
61 areas with high organic aerosol and RH levels (Kakavas et al., 2022). The importance
62 of these SOAW impacts on secondary aerosol formations has not been systematically
63 studied and is the focus of this work.

64 We use a new aerosol thermodynamics model, ISORROPIA-lite (Kakavas et
65 al., 2022), to simulate SOAW effects on the partitioning of the inorganic components,
66 for a year over the continental United States. The model performance has been
67 evaluated for fine PM and its components for the examined period by Skyllakou et al.
68 (2021). It is considered good for the total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration and average for most of
69 the components. The aim of our work is to quantify the SOAW contribution to the

70 total fine PM water and to study its effects on inorganic aerosol thermodynamics and
71 total dry fine PM levels and composition.

72

73 **2. Methods**

74 **2.1 ISORROPIA-lite**

75 ISORROPIA-lite is a lean and accelerated version of the widely used ISORROPIA-II
76 (Fountoukis and Nenes, 2007) aerosol thermodynamics model and it focuses on the
77 simulation of the thermodynamic equilibrium of inorganic atmospheric aerosol. It
78 assumes that the aerosol exists only in the metastable state at low RH and the activity
79 coefficients of ionic pairs are always obtained from precalculated look-up tables. It
80 estimates aerosol water associated with each one of the aerosol components.
81 Furthermore, ISORROPIA-lite has an important additional feature compared to
82 ISORROPIA-II, as it considers the effects of SOAW on inorganic aerosol
83 thermodynamics. The resulting increase of the total water mass drives more of the
84 water-soluble gaseous species to the particle phase to satisfy equilibrium. SOAW,
85 W_{SOA} , in ISORROPIA-lite is calculated using the well-established κ -Kohler theory of
86 Petters and Kreidenweis (2007):

$$87 \quad W_{SOA} = \frac{\rho_w}{\rho_{SOA}} \frac{C_{SOA} \kappa}{\left(\frac{1}{RH} - 1\right)} \quad (1)$$

88 where ρ_w is the density of water, ρ_{SOA} the SOA density, C_{SOA} the SOA concentration, κ
89 the SOA hygroscopicity parameter and RH the relative humidity in the 0–1 scale.
90 More details about the ISORROPIA-lite can be found in Kakavas et al. (2022).

91

92 **2.2 PMCAMx description and application**

93 PMCAMx (Karydis et al., 2010; Tsimpidi et al., 2010) is a three dimensional
94 chemical transport model based on CAMx (Environ, 2006), which simulates
95 horizontal and vertical advection and dispersion, dry and wet deposition, as well as
96 aqueous, gas, and aerosol chemistry. The mechanism used in this work for gas-phase
97 chemistry simulations is the Carbon Bond 05 (CB5) (Yarwood et al., 2005) and
98 includes 190 reactions of 79 gas species. To describe the aerosol size and composition
99 distribution 10-size sections (from 40 nm to 40 μ m) are used assuming that all
100 particles in each size bin have the same composition. Therefore, PMCAMx predicts
101 PM_x concentrations where x can be among other choices 1, 2.5 and 10 μ m.

102 Equilibrium is always assumed between the bulk aerosol and gas phases. The
103 partitioning of semi-volatile inorganic species between the gas and particulate phases
104 is simulated by ISORROPIA-lite. Weighting factors based on each size bin's effective
105 surface area are used to distribute to the various size bins the mass transferred
106 between the two phases in each time step (Pandis et al., 1993). For the simulation of
107 organic aerosols, the volatility basis set (VBS) approach (Donahue et al., 2006) is
108 used. POA is simulated using eight volatility bins (from 10^{-1} to $10^6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) at 298 K,
109 while for SOA four volatility bins ($1, 10, 10^2, 10^3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) at 298 K are used (Murphy
110 and Pandis, 2009). An organic aerosol phase is assumed with its components forming
111 a pseudo-ideal solution and being in equilibrium with the gas phase (Strader et al.,
112 1998). The influence of water on the partitioning of the organic components of the
113 particulate matter between the gas and aerosol phases is assumed to be negligible in
114 this version of PMCAMx (Koo et al., 2003). The low volatility organic compounds
115 (LVOCs) and the extremely LVOCs are implicitly included in the lowest volatility bin
116 of this version of the VBS used in PMCAMx. These compounds are always in the
117 particulate phase in these simulations and therefore the addition of lower bins
118 increases the computational cost without changing the predicted organic aerosol
119 concentration. For the major point sources, the NO_x plumes are simulated using the
120 Plume-in-Grid (PiG) approach (Karamchandani et al., 2011; Zakoura and
121 Pandis, 2019). The variable size resolution model (VSRM) of Fahey and Pandis
122 (2001) is used for the simulation of aqueous-phase. The model is based on the
123 chemical mechanism of Pandis and Seinfeld (1989) with the addition of Ca^{2+} to the
124 list of particle components as well as H_2SO_4 in the gas phase (Fahey and Pandis,
125 2001).

126 We applied PMCAMx over the continental United States during 2010. The
127 modeling domain includes northern Mexico and southern Canada and covers a $4752 \times$
128 2952 km^2 region (Figure S1). The model grid consists of 10,824 cells with horizontal
129 dimensions of $36 \times 36 \text{ km}$. The meteorological inputs were provided by the Weather
130 Research Forecasting model (WRF v3.6.1) using a horizontal resolution of $12 \times$
131 12 km . RH levels above 95% were rare therefore there was no need for screening of
132 the few high RH values outside clouds. The gaseous and primary particle emissions
133 were developed by Xing et al. (2013). More details about the meteorological inputs
134 and the emissions can be found in Skyllakou et al. (2021).

135 To quantify the SOAW effects on inorganic aerosol thermodynamics three
136 simulations were performed. The first was a simulation neglecting SOAW and
137 including only inorganic aerosol water. Two additional simulations were performed:
138 one where κ of SOA was assumed to be equal to 0.1 and one with $\kappa=0.2$ (Kuang et al.,
139 2020) to examine how SOA hygroscopicity affects total fine aerosol water content
140 and PM levels and composition. Even if higher values of the hygroscopicity
141 parameter (e.g., $\kappa=0.3$) are possible (Kuang et al., 2020) these represent rather
142 extreme cases for the simulation of the average effects over the US. Therefore, the
143 two simulations used in this study provide a good estimate of the corresponding
144 uncertainty. Previous studies have estimated secondary organic aerosol density values
145 of 1–1.4 g cm⁻³ (Turpin and Lim, 2001; Kostenidou et al., 2007). A SOA density of 1
146 g cm⁻³ was assumed in the simulations. The SOA exists mostly in submicrometer
147 particles so our subsequent study focuses on PM₁.

148

149 **3. Results**

150 **3.1 Effects of SOAW on PM₁ water levels**

151 The annual average PM₁ water ground-level concentrations neglecting SOAW are
152 shown in Figure 1. Higher PM₁ water concentrations from 8 to 18 μg m⁻³ are
153 predicted in the north-eastern part of the US due to the higher inorganic PM₁
154 concentrations (Figure 2) and RH levels in that area. When SOAW is present in the
155 simulations, total PM₁ water levels increase everywhere with higher fractional
156 increases in the south-eastern US (up to 50% when $\kappa=0.1$ and up to 100% when $\kappa=0.2$
157 in Alabama and north-western Mexico) due to higher SOA levels (Figure S2). In the
158 north-eastern US, lower fractional increases are predicted (10–15% when $\kappa=0.1$ and
159 20–30% when $\kappa=0.2$). In general, assuming a κ of SOA equal to 0.2 instead of 0.1
160 increases the corresponding amount of SOAW by about a factor of two. Figure 1
161 shows the distributions of fractional increase change in the annual PM₁ water levels at
162 ground level from SOAW. Total PM₁ water average concentrations increase from 20
163 to 30% in about 60% of the modeling domain when $\kappa=0.1$. For $\kappa=0.2$, the
164 corresponding increase is from 40 to 60%.

165 Predicted SOA levels are higher during summertime (Figure S2) since the
166 emissions and oxidation rates of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) are higher
167 (Zhang et al., 2013; Freney et al., 2014; Skyllakou et al., 2014; Fountoukis et al.,
168 2016). However, even during wintertime fresh biomass burning emissions exposed to

169 NO₂ and O₃ can form significant amounts of SOA in periods with low OH levels
170 (Kodros et al., 2020). Higher total PM₁ water concentrations are predicted during
171 winter (Figure 3) since the RH levels and inorganic fine aerosol concentrations are
172 higher; especially nitrate and chloride which increasingly partition to the aerosol
173 phase as temperature decreases (Guo et al., 2017). However, PM₁ chloride
174 concentrations are low (less than 0.1 μg m⁻³) with higher concentrations in Kansas
175 because of biomass burning episodes. Higher fractional increases in fine aerosol water
176 levels (up to 5 times) due to SOAW are predicted during summer in the south-eastern
177 part of US where SOA concentrations are higher. This corresponds to increases to
178 average fine aerosol water concentrations up to 8 μg m⁻³.

179 Ammonium nitrate and ammonium sulfate are the inorganic salts that
180 contribute the most to the total PM₁ water levels (Figure S3). SOAW also contributes
181 significantly to the total PM₁ water levels especially in the south-eastern US (about 30
182 and 50% of total PM₁ water when κ=0.1 and κ=0.2 respectively), when the mass
183 fraction of SOA in dry PM₁ exceeds 30%.

184

185 **3.2 Effects of SOAW on total dry PM₁ levels**

186 Higher dry PM₁ concentrations are predicted for the eastern part of the US (up to 15
187 μg m⁻³) in the base case (Figure 4). These dry PM₁ levels increase slightly up to 0.6%
188 and 1.2% due to SOAW when κ=0.1 and κ=0.2 for SOA is assumed. The highest
189 annual average fractional increase in total dry PM₁ levels is predicted in California
190 (1% when κ=0.1 and 2% when κ=0.2). The probability density (Figure 4) indicates
191 that in about 60% of the modeling domain total dry fine aerosol concentrations
192 increase up to 0.3% when κ=0.1. For κ=0.2, the corresponding increase is from 0.4 to
193 2%. The areas of the highest PM₁ increase correspond to regions where aerosol pH
194 tends to be relatively high (Pye et al., 2020). In these areas, nitric acid and ammonia
195 can condense and increase aerosol mass because of the increase in water from the
196 SOA. Because of this partitioning change, the predicted gas-phase concentrations of
197 semi-volatile inorganic components decreased on average when SOAW was
198 considered (Figure S4). SOAW had a negligible absolute impact on the small fine
199 chloride concentrations in this period (Figure 2). However, in periods during which
200 chloride salts and SOA contribute significantly to the total dry (e.g. during intense
201 biomass burning periods), fine chloride concentrations could also change (Metzger et
202 al., 2006; Fountoukis et al., 2009; Gunthe et al., 2021).

203 Skyllakou et al. (2021) found that PMCAMx had a small fractional bias (5%)
204 and a fractional error (25%) for the annual average PM_{2.5} concentrations of 1067
205 measurements stations in the U.S. The performance of PMCAMx regarding annual
206 average OA is considered good in these simulations with a fractional bias of 5% and a
207 fractional error of 26% in the 306 stations in the US. For daily average concentrations
208 the performance is also quite encouraging with a fractional bias of 15% and a
209 fractional error of 56%. Given that the effect of the extension of the model on the total
210 fine PM mass is small (of the order of 1%), this does not result in any noticeable
211 change in its already very good performance for dry fine PM. Therefore, the major
212 change in the model predictions is on the aerosol water concentrations.

213

214 **3.3 Effects of SOAW on PM₁ components**

215 The annual average results indicate that SOAW mainly affects fine aerosol water
216 levels. To better analyze the effects of SOAW we focus on the temporal evolution of
217 the predicted levels of PM₁ components in four sites (Figure S1) with different
218 characteristics (Table S1). We have chosen one city from the West, one from the
219 South, one from Southeast and one from the Northeast. They are all in different
220 environments with different major sources and climatological conditions. The
221 presence of SOAW increased PM₁ water concentrations in all sites from 1% to almost
222 an order of magnitude (Figure 5). However, these fractional increases most of the
223 time correspond to PM₁ water concentration increases of a few $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (Figure S5)
224 because they occur under low RH levels. During higher RH periods (80 to 100%), the
225 PM₁ water levels are predicted to increase up to $100 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (e.g. in Toronto).

226 Total dry PM₁ concentrations during most of the simulated period increase on
227 average less than 1% in all sites (Figure 5) due to SOAW. There are periods, however,
228 with higher fractional increases (up to 10%) and even small decreases (up to 5%) in
229 total dry fine aerosol levels in the examined sites. The decreases can be explained
230 because SOAW increases the size of particles and therefore their dry deposition rate
231 (Nenes et al., 2020). Depending on SOA hygroscopicity, increases up to $1.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
232 for nitrate and $0.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ for ammonium are predicted (Figure S5). Fine nitrate
233 increases of 10% were more frequent in the examined sites; however higher increases
234 up to 200% are predicted during the simulated period (Figure 6). As expected, higher
235 increases can occur more often with higher assumed SOA hygroscopicity.

236

237 **4. Discussion**

238 Aerosol liquid water has a profound impact on aerosol processes, chemical
239 composition and their impacts. By including the effects of organic water on
240 inorganics thermodynamic equilibrium we show that SOAW can substantially
241 increase aerosol water levels, on an average up to 60% over the majority of the
242 domain. As a consequence, total dry PM_{10} levels can also increase but the changes are
243 small (up to 2% on an annual average basis). Locally these effects can be much more
244 significant during periods of high RH and SOA levels (fine nitrate fractional increases
245 can be as high as 200%).

246 The effects vary with season. During summer, the RH is lower and SOA levels
247 are higher leading to higher fractional increases in aerosol water (Figure 3) but lower
248 absolute mass changes. During summer the fractional increases in total dry fine
249 aerosol concentrations are lower than in wintertime (Figure S6). Responsible for the
250 total dry fine aerosol concentration increases are nitrate and ammonium (Figure 2).
251 These compounds partition together (as deliquesced ammonium nitrate) to the
252 particulate phase to satisfy equilibrium due to the additional water mass of SOA.

253 The increases in total dry PM_{10} and fine aerosol water levels depend on SOA
254 concentrations, hygroscopicity value, RH levels and the particle phase fractions of
255 inorganic species. The SOAW effect on aerosol water is approximately proportional
256 to the assumed hygroscopicity parameter κ . Given that our work investigates the
257 potential significance of this effect we have chosen to provide the results of two
258 simulations one with relatively low and relatively high hygroscopicity of SOA. A
259 more detailed treatment of the hygroscopicity parameter (e.g., assigning a different
260 value to each OA component) will be a topic of future work.

261 The present work, thoroughly analyzes organic water uptake impacts over one
262 simulated year (not just one month as done in Kakavas et al., 2022) and in quite a
263 different geographical area (US here versus Europe in Kakavas et al., 2022). There are
264 significant differences, but also similarities in the predicted changes and effects of
265 SOA water. Both studies indicate that SOAW can contribute highly to the total PM_{10}
266 water and increase particulate nitrate concentrations especially in areas with high total
267 nitrate concentrations. Pilinis et al. (1995) have argued that the single most important
268 parameter in determining direct aerosol forcing is RH, and the most important process
269 is the increase of the aerosol mass as a result of water uptake. They estimated that on
270 average an increase of the RH from 40 to 80% for a global mean aerosol more than

271 doubles the corresponding radiative forcing. As a result the inclusion of SOAW in
272 future studies is highly recommended. ISORROPIA-lite provides a simple and
273 computationally effective approach for the simulation of this SOAW.

274

275 **Code and Data Availability.** The model code and data used in this study are available
276 from the authors upon request (spyros@chemeng.upatras.gr and
277 athanasios.nenes@epfl.ch).

278

279 **Author Contributions.** SK incorporated ISORROPIA-lite in PMCAMx, carried out the
280 simulations, analyzed the results and wrote the manuscript. SN and AN conceived and
281 led the study and helped in the writing of the manuscript.

282

283 **Competing Interests.** The authors declare no competing financial interest.

284

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506 **Figure 1.** Maps of: (a) annual average PM₁ water ground-level concentrations
507 neglecting SOAW, (b) annual average fractional increase of PM₁ water when SOAW
508 is present in the simulations with $\kappa=0.1$ and, (c) with $\kappa=0.2$ during 2010. The
509 probability density as a function of fractional increase in the annual PM₁ water
510 concentrations due to SOAW when: (d) $\kappa=0.1$ and (e) $\kappa=0.2$ is shown.

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532 **Figure 2.** Annual average ground-level concentrations (in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) of PM₁: (a) nitrate,
 533 (b) ammonium, (c) sulfate, and (d) chloride neglecting SOAW and the annual
 534 concentration changes when SOAW is present in the simulations with $\kappa=0.1$ and
 535 $\kappa=0.2$. A positive change corresponds to an increase. A negative change corresponds
 536 to a decrease.

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545 **Figure 3.** Average ground-level concentrations of PM₁ water neglecting SOAW (in
 546 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and the fractional increase when SOAW is present in the simulations with
 547 $\kappa=0.1$ and $\kappa=0.2$ during: (a) autumn (SON), (b) winter (DJF), (c) spring (MAM), and
 548 (d) summer (JJA) of 2010.

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561 **Figure 4.** Maps of: (a) annual average total dry PM₁ ground-level concentrations
562 neglecting SOAW, (b) annual average fractional increase of total dry PM₁ when
563 SOAW is present in the simulations with $\kappa=0.1$ and, (c) with $\kappa=0.2$ during 2010. The
564 probability density as a function of fractional increase in the annual total dry PM₁
565 concentrations due to SOAW when: (d) $\kappa=0.1$ and (e) $\kappa=0.2$ is shown.

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594 **Figure 5.** Box plots for fractional change in the hourly: **(a)** PM₁ water and **(b)** total
595 dry PM₁ due to SOAW when $\kappa=0.1$ and $\kappa=0.2$ for Sacramento, California; Houston,
596 Texas; Atlanta, Georgia; and Toronto, Canada during 2010. The red line represents
597 the median, the black dot is the mean value, the upper box line is the upper quartile
598 (75%) and the lower box line is the lower quartile (25%) of the distribution. A
599 negative change corresponds to a decrease.

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617 **Figure 6.** The probability density as a function of fractional increase in the hourly
618 PM_1 nitrate due to SOAW when $\kappa=0.1$ and $\kappa=0.2$ for: (a) Sacramento, California; (b)
619 Houston, Texas; (c) Atlanta, Georgia; and (d) Toronto, Canada during 2010.